

Correlation of Consumer Type and Consumption Decision Process

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 03 July 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Nirwana</p>	<p>What will you do when you plan a holiday to Bali Island. Preparation of how it should be done so that the plan journey tour goes smoothly and get a nice holiday. Surely there is thorough planning and preparation related with the holiday. In the decision process consumer something planning and preparation is a problem that leads to an objective. As well as with consumer before get expected product will face a series of problems related with product. A problem is part from its cause and effect and use product. Why consumer need product and how the process follows when will get product. As well as the process that will take place happen after obtain desired product. According to Kotler, there is a series of activities performed when consumer do purchase (<i>consumer purchase decision process</i>). A series of activities that covers introduction problem (<i>problem recognition</i>), collecting information (<i>information search</i>), evaluation to alternative information (<i>valuation of alternatives</i>), purchase (<i>purchase decision</i>), and behavior after purchase (<i>postpurchase behavior</i>).</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Consumer Type, Decision Process, behavior</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Retrieval process decision purchase started from exists problem (*problem recognition*). Problem is a factor pusher for do something. Problem consumer related with exists needs and desires to brands and products. When somebody will traveling to something a place far away considered far. So required tool transportation for reach place the need to tool transportation is answer from exists problem reach place the with thereby can concluded exists problem is beginning from exists needs and desires to products that can finish problem.

There is needs and desires to something product leads to search information (*information search*) about product. Search and collection information can obtained from provider product, for example from information promotion. But information is also available obtained party others, like from fellow consumer, or reference party other. Media provider information moment this enough many and varied. In line with progress technology information, such as television, internet. Surely very help consumer in get supporting information in solution problem.

Step furthermore in the decision process consumption is do activity evaluation to alternative information (*evaluation of an alternative*). Information already collected will done evaluation based on level needs and interests. Resulting evaluation in form a number of alternative required information. Because it does not require all information already obtained used all. Purchasing

(*purchased decision*) is part most importantly from results decision purchases. Activities purchase covers time purchase, location purchase, type product, alternative product chosen.

Once done purchase next with behavior after purchase (*postpurchase behavior*). It happened purchase product No means consumer No continue the decision process purchase. After purchase consumer will do evaluation to products that have been purchased. Evaluation after purchase produce conclusion to continuation consumption on the product. If consumer give evaluation Good to product. Then is indication beginning exists satisfaction. So that No close possibility will happen purchase repeat. Whereas If evaluation consumer give doubts about the product of course consumer will do consideration repeat to use product. But if consumer give evaluation product because product considered No give satisfaction. Form risk from exists dissatisfaction consumer will stop purchase to product.

As example from the retrieval process decision purchases made a traveler with the plan for go to Bali. At first exists desire for fill in day his holiday with activity tourism. The emergence desire for travel is problems solved by tourists the. Problem related for realize desire fill in holiday with travel. Desire travel push traveler search and collect information related with plan journey tour the. Information can collected from various source. Information can obtained from brochures issued by service bureaus journey tours, flyers package tour from manager tour. As well as from electronic media like browsing internet places objective

interesting tour. With all instructions for planned tourism programs. Covers transportation, accommodation, event activities tour when until in place objective tour. After the collection process information considered complete. Whole information will be evaluated based on relationships and interests information with plan tour. After considering Enough evaluation choice information based on relationships and interests from information the. Traveler will determine choice package product expected tour the. Consideration time energy, cost, and power pull Of course become base in determine product tour. Like Visit to object tour beaches, lakes, mountains, attractions culture local. After enjoying holiday travel to island to the island of Bali. Traveler will evaluate journey the tour satisfying or no satisfying. If during travel feel pleasant benefits Of course will give evaluation satisfying. Will follow up with visit to same place. On the contrary If during travel No obtain satisfaction. Traveler No repeat travel in the same place.

Consumer Decision Perspective

is consumer follow linear steps in the retrieval process decision consumption. From several case purchase No all decision process steps the used consumer. Moreover if consumer Already very know brands and products. As well as have undergo purchase in a way periodic and deep relatively long time. But No means the retrieval process decision linear consumption No used again by consumers. According to *Mowen* there is a number of perspective on retrieval decision. Among them *perspective taking decision traditional* which includes *decision involvement low (low involvement decision)* and *decisions involvement high (high involvement decision)*, *perspective taking decision experience (experiential perspective)*, and *perspective influence behavior (behavior influence perspective)*

When consumer do purchase follow stages in the retrieval process decision. Started from know problem, collect information, evaluation information, purchasing, and evaluation after purchase. Show If consumer use perspective taking decision in a way traditional. In perspective traditional there is two possible decision process purchase. Consumer do with *involvement low (low involvement decision)*. It means consumer simplify the decision process. Decision process done with A little involvement in choice brands and products. Understanding from involvement show roles and interests consumer to brand and type product. Engagement low show consumer not enough notice brand and type product. Vice versa involvement tall means consumer notice existence brands and various type product as material consideration. Acquisition decision involvement low depending on the level introduction to brands and products. The more known brand and product picking process decision done with involvement low. Price product join in influence decision in a way with involvement low. Product with price cheap decision process purchase more simple rather than expensive products

Decision process purchase with *involvement high (high involvement decision)*. Involvement tall to consideration brand and consideration product. Consumer will carry out the evaluation process before decide purchase. Start from introduction problem in a way deep, collecting information brands and products in a way broad. Do evaluation choice information in a way record. Do purchase with comparison brands and also comparison product. With an evaluation process after purchase done in a way deep.

Perspective *taking decision experience* done consumers who have experienced in understand brand and product. Share consumer knowledge about brands and products Already considered enough. Then No required Lots information related with use brands and products. Influence experience from use brands and products give impact on the retrieval process decision purchase. So when done purchase next is part from refinement purchase previously. So that consumer will more Jelly about brands and products. Introduction problem around How experience problem brands and products previously. Search process information based on solution problem from purchase previously. Alternative evaluation is a comparison process from experience about brands and products. Choice brands and products based on impact experience previously.

Perspective *influence behavior* more emphasizes factors behavior consumers. So the collection process decision more tend influenced by behavior consumer. introduction problem based on characteristics behavior consumer. between One consumer with another consumer occurs difference in understand problem brands and products. Search information more on the response that has been studied. With evaluation more alternatives nature results behavior from empowerment himself. Meanwhile choice brands and products controlled by perception consumer.

Type Consumer

Behavior consumer in the decision process purchase No always follow linear flow in the consumption process. Deep linear flow taking decision started from introduction problem, looking for information, evaluation information, purchasing, and evaluation after purchase. Because consumers own different attitudes and views to brand and product. According to *Mowen* there is a number of type from consumer based on engagement consumer. Involvement consumer to brand and product. Engagement consumer in evaluate existence brand. Constitute effort consumer For compare brand, loyalty to the brand certain, even brand rejection specific. Involvement consumers on the brand is evaluation consumer to brand that lasts This known and moderate promoted by the seller. Meanwhile involvement consumers on the product is part form assessment of quality product, form physique product, benefits products, as well convenience use product. Shape involvement tall indicated If attention to brands and products high. Meanwhile involvement low indicated attention to brands and products

low or not enough pay attention. Following there is a number of type consumer based on engagement on brands and products.

Complex buying behavior (buying complicated), is a form of behavior high consumer in brand engagement. Consumer Not Enough compare brand but also looking Lots alternative brands available. And engagement with the product is also high, meaning consumer more thorough in look for advantages and weaknesses from product. Start from packaging, price, benefits, service, and specifications product supporting it. Usually characteristic behavior complex This carried out by consumers who will consume goods with mark expensive economy. Like purchase car luxury, apartment, or do journey tour with budget high. But No close possibility factor characteristics consumer join in determine behavior complex purchases. For example exists attitude hesitant to products and tends give negative assessment to product

Variety seeking buying behavior (Behavior buy who is looking for diversity), behavior This leads to engagement low on the product, but engagement with the brand Enough high. Pg This intended For get various alternative brand. Or try existence brand that lasts This Not yet known. Consumer tend not enough notice product, form physique product, benefits products, as well convenience use product. Condition This show If consumer want to try a number of brand. Product consumed tend product with mark economy cheap. Like bath soap, wall paint, supplies House ladder with mark economy cheap, perfume, and equipment electricity.

Dissonance reducing buying behavior (Behavior buy For reduce mismatch), type buyer thereby involvement in the product tend tall. This matter done For reduce risk product. Like risk physical, risk time, risk financial, and risk function product. Meanwhile engagement with the brand tend low. Meaning consumer No important existence brand. Share consumer type This interest main is existence product. form physique product, benefits products, as well convenience use product. Example type consumer This is on purchase rare product used but own mark relatively expensive economy. Like purchase furniture House stairs, carpets, ceramics, and also purchases fence House stay.

Habitual buying behavior (Behavior buy based on habits), part from behavior frequent purchases done consumers in general. Consumer only need involvement low to brand and also on the product. Share consumer existence brand Already very known, or on the contrary No important For get to know him. Because what's important consumer is benefit product. Meanwhile low involvement in the product. Reflects that product the of course has often utilized in life all day. So enough emphasis facet functions and benefits product. Type purchase like This occurs in valuable products economy relatively cheap. And characteristic the product of course required in activity everyday life. For example purchase of products paper tissue, motorbike shampoo, skewer teeth, and soap wash.

CONCLUSION

Retrieval process decision purchase can done individually or collectively group. Individually show consumer run the retrieval process decision with No involve group in a way direct. Meanwhile the retrieval process decision purchases made in a way group. Done with share roles and interests every individuals involved in the purchasing process. Kotler outlines the retrieval process decision purchase in a way group share role every individual. Start from *attention, interest, decision*, etc *purchase* done a number of individual. Although later those who are interested to purchase product only a individual. For example, in One consisting of families from father, mother, children, and servants House ladder. Family This planned traveling go out city with utilise service transportation train fire. Consumption process service train fire started exists attention (attention) a child to service service train fire. After going through the attention process possibility Mother interested (*interested*) to service the. And prosecuted followed by the decision process *from* the father towards use service train fire. After my father decided to use service train fire For traveling. So a servant House the stairs given task For do action purchase (action) ticket train necessary fire them.

Activity or process before purchasing, purchasing process and after process purchase service. Tightly connection with influencing factors behavior consumer services. Existence factors the No close possibility consumer do decision purchase. Or otherwise, no do decision purchasing. Factors influence purchase can originate from internal and external. *Kotler* identify factors influence behavior consumer into five groups. Among them group cultural, social, personal, psychological and buyer That Alone. As well as for subgroups cultural has subcultures and classes social. Whereas factor social consists from subgroups reference, family, role and status. Factor psychological consists from subgroups motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes.

Factor culture is element base in guide somebody do something action. Culture reflect level understanding of activities life. Factor culture can covers subculture, culture, class social. *Culture* is factor decider main in translate desires and needs person. Culture or culture very tightly with traditions in the environment around, like family, friends, associations. So possibility between one person to another. Tends different Because factor influence more scope small the. Section smallest of culture is *subculture*, so subculture can consists from a number of group influential individual directly to the individual other. They own inclined views and judgments The same. *Social class*, namely relative arrangement structured and orderly in order public. With put forward aspect relative values, interests, and behavior The same. Social class No limited to aspects economics, however covers more aspects broad. Like level income, welfare, education, and relative habits No Far different.

Factor social show existence individual in group social , group giver references , family , relatives , groups , as well as more groups wide . Existence individual in group determine behavior individual in consume. Decision process consumer based on habit from group. Even existence group made as material reference in consume.Role group Enough important in influence decision consumption. Available mark satisfaction If own similarity with group when decide brands and products consumed. Aspects social also reflects on *roles* in environment and *status* life social.

Factor personal part from that which is inherent in the individual, such as age and stage cycle life, position, circumstances economy, style life, personality, and concepts self. *Age and stage cycle live*, someone experiencing a marked life process exists age. Based on age can done grouping age children, adults and the elderly. There is factor age pattern consumption also occurs difference. Product earmarked for children, products earmarked for adults, and also products earmarked for parents. Meanwhile based on stage cycle life will experience a number of stage or phase. Like phase toddler, phase children, phase adolescence, phase adulthood, and phase old. Stages cycle life somebody influential to product consumed. So happen change pattern and type consumed products in line with development phase the. *Attitude*, decisive pattern consumption from consumer.Strategy marketing directed For know attitude consumer to brand and product. Mix promotion realized in frame answer attitude consumers.as well as expected capable create positive attitude to brands and products. Attitude positive interpreted as can attitude receive and use brand and product.According to Schiffman and Kanuk (1997) attitude is expression from feelings (*inner feeling*), as well as reflect view somebody like or No happy , like or do n't agree or No to something object.For example If linked with brand and product , then form attitude can form Like or No Like to brand and product.With thereby attitude very determine the decision process consumption.

Factor psychological covers motivation, perception, learning, and beliefs. *Motivation* according to Solomon (1999) is a causal process somebody do like he did do. And motivation is stimulation mover somebody For act, cooperate, work effective and integrated For reach expected goal. *Perception*, is part from evaluation somebody to something object.Then there is trend If evaluation to something object between one person to another relatively No The same . Perception can also be interpreted as something Suite selecting, explaining and giving conclusion something object

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